

Armenian *Dorcadion* (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) of “*cinerarium*-group”

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Abstract. The “group-*cinerarium*” is represented by three species in Armenia: *Dorcadion* (*Cribridorcadion*) *kasikoporanum* Pic, 1902 (Arailer Mt. near Erevan), *D. (C.) sisianense* sp. n. (Sisian pass) and *D. (C.) megridense* sp. n. (Megri ridge). Both new species are close to European *D. (C.) cinerarium* (Fabricius, 1787), but differ by relatively smooth dorsal body side, nearly total absence of pubescent form of females and endophallic structure. All three species differ from each other by the peculiarities of elytral and pronotal sculpture. *D. (C.) megridense* sp. n. is characterized by very big size. *D. (C.) cinerarium* (F.) is redescribed, its area is specified. The absence of *D. (C.) cinerarium* in Armenia and Georgia is stated; all previous records of the species for both republics (as well as for Turkey) were connected with wrong determinations of closely related species. *D. (C.) caucasicum* Küster, 1847 is regarded as a subspecies of *D. (C.) sulcipenne* Küster, 1847: *D. (C.) sulcipenne caucasicum* Küster, 1847, stat. n. Lectotype is designated for *Lamia cineraria* Fabricius, 1787.

INTRODUCTION

The present paper concerns three species, which belong to a large group of taxa close to *Dorcadion cinerarium* (Fabricius, 1787). “*D. cinerarium*-group” of species is characterized by usually glabrous male elytra with white sutural stripe followed by velvety-black subsutural lines; females often autochromal (with densely pubescent elytra); legs and first antennal joint usually red. The species of the group are distributed from central and south Europe to Near East.

Dorcadion cinerarium (Fabricius, 1787) was described (Fig. 1) as *Lamia cineraria* Fabricius, 1787 on the base of one female from South Russia (“Habitat in Russia meridionali”), received by Fabricius from Hybner (“Dom. Hybner”), and on the base of a female (Fig. 2) figured by P. Pallas (1781): “Pallas Icon, tab. F. fig II”. So, two syntypes were mentioned in the original description.

I have managed to receive for study the type female (Fig. 3) from Universitetes Zoologiske Museum, København (preserved before in Germany in Kiel Museum) with a single hand written label (Fabricius hand): “*cineraria*” (Fig. 4) and another printed label “Kiel II. 300.102”, that is typical for the types by Fabricius. This female does not belong to the species,

which is traditionally known as *D. cinerarium*. It belongs to the species later described as *D. pusillum* Küster, 1847, which is also rather numerous in South Russia and Ukraine. Such form of *D. pusillum* (without black spots along sutural elytral stripe) was recently described as *D. pusillum tanaiticum* Kasatkin, 2002 from Rostov region of Russia.

Second syntype (Fig. 2), figured schematically by Pallas (1781) without any name and without any text at all, is without any doubt a female of just same species, which is generally accepted now as *Dorcadion cinerarium*. This female is characterized by diffuse white wide elytral stripes, that is often typical for females of *D. cinerarium*, and differs from *D. elegans* Kraatz, 1873 (another local species with stripped elytra), which is also common in the region and has narrow contrast white stripes. Besides the lateral thoracic tubercles of the figured female are rather wide, not attenuated apically, similar to *D. cinerarium*, while in *D. pusillum* and *D. elegans* lateral thoracic tubercles are strongly attenuated and narrow apically.

I have designated as lectotype a female (Fig. 2) figured by Pallas (1781: tab. F., fig. 11), so the stability of the nomenclature is maintained. I do not know that female, but it does not make my designation not valid (ICZN, 1999: 82; Article 74.4).

Another type female (Fig. 3) from København Museum, identified by me as *D. pusillum tanaiticum* Kasatkin, 2002, is designated now as paralectotype of *Lamia cineraria* Fabricius, 1787.

So, the sense of the name *Dorcadion cinerarium* (Fabricius, 1787) rests traditional.

The picture of lectotype (Fig. 2) was not followed by any text, so the type locality rests now uncertain. I preliminary accept as type locality the south territory of European Russia of XVIII century (now it is Ukraine and South Russia) according to the title of the publication by Pallas (1781): “Icones insectorum praesertim Rossiae Sibiriaque peculiarium”, and according to the fact that similar *Dorcadion* is absent in Siberia and Central Russia.

The text to the picture by Pallas can be discovered in unpublished manuscripts preserved in Berlin Zoological Museum.

Plavilstshikov (1958) used for this species the name *D. caucasicum* Küster, 1847 because according to his opinion the old name by Fabricius was forgotten long ago and more over pubescent form of female is not desirable as a type for this species. So, the species is well known now as *D. caucasicum*; this name was often used in relatively modern publications (Lobanov et al., 1982; Zahaikévitch, 1991; Prisnyj, 2005).

The name *D. cinerarium* (F.) was restored by Breuning (1946: 117), who adequately described the type female from Fabricius collection in Kiel. He often used it in his publications (Breuning, 1958, 1962; Breuning & Villiers 1967; Fuchs & Breuning, 1971). The name was also accepted by many new and old authors (Küster, 1848; Perissinotto & Luchini, 1966; Demelt, 1967; Danilevsky, 1996; Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985; Althoff & Danilevsky, 1997; Bartenev, 2004; Danilevsky et al., 2005; Özdikmen, 2007). Ganglbauer (1884: 443) also supposed the name „*D. cinerarium* Fabr.“ as original for the species.

D. cinerarium includes a lot of rather different populations distributed from Voronezh region to Krasnodar region and through Ukraine to Moldova in the West. The east border of the species area must be the river Volga as no specimens are known eastwards the Volga. Many very dense populations of *D. cinerarium* are known from many regions of South Russia and Ukraine; the species is very common in Crimea. Many *Dorcadion* populations from Turkey and North Iran (originally described as different species) were wrongly regarded as

cineraria. 45. L. thorace spinoso cinerascens, antennis breuibus,
Pallas Icon, tab. F. fig. 11.
Habitat in Russia meridionali Dom. Hybner.
Statura et summa affinitas praecedentis, at duplo fere
minor et totum corpus cinerascens.

Figs 1-4. 1- Original description of *Lamia cineraria* F. 2- Picture (Pallas, 1771) of *Lamia cineraria* F. (female, lectotype). 3- *Dorcadion pusillum tanaiticum*, female, paralectotype (present designation) of *Lamia cineraria* F. 4- The unique label of the paralectotype of *Lamia cineraria* F.

different forms of *D. cinerarium* (*D. micans* Thomson, 1867; *D. sericatum* Kraatz, 1873; *D. macropus* Kraatz, 1873), as *D. cinerarium* does not penetrate already in Transcaucasia. All *Dorcadion* populations from Iran and Turkey, which were attributed before to *D. cinerarium* (often as its subspecies, variations, morphs, forms or aberrations) belong to another partly

not described species, which differ by elytral and pronotal sculpture, body shape and body size, genital structures, and usually total dominations of glabrous form of females, which are rather rare in *D. cinerarium*.

D. cinerarium is well represented in museum collections. Hundreds of specimens from Russia and Ukraine were found by me among undetermined materials in Zoological Museum of Moscow University and in Zoological Institute of Sankt-Petersburg and installed in basic collections.

While describing studied materials (look below) I have listed only selected data from the most important localities as the whole number of available specimens is too much. The precise citation of available labels was used only for type materials; in other cases I have recorded for each specimen its sex, the exact name of locality, date of collection (if available), name of collector (if available) and the place of preservation. Most of original labels are in Russian with different orthography of same geographical names with various abbreviations.

According to Plavilstshikov (1958) the area of the species (as “*D. caucasicum*”) occupies «the whole Caucasus from Don Steppe and Ciscaucasia to Transcaucasia”. But neither Plavilstshikov’s collection in Zoological Museum of Moscow University, nor collection of Zoological Museum in Sankt-Petersburg contain any specimens of *D. cinerarium* from Georgia or Armenia. More over Plavilstshikov identified as “*D. caucasicum*” many specimens of *D. sulcipenne* Küster, 1847a from near Tbilisi - males with glabrous elytra, which can be called *D. sulcipenne* m. *exsertum* Plavilstshikov, 1948. A part of such glabrous specimens was reliably treated by him as *D. sulcipenne* (mostly females), but another part of glabrous specimens from same populations (mostly males) as *D. caucasicum*.

In fact it is evident now that two forms of *D. sulcipenne* (glabrous and pubescent) were originally described as two different species: *D. caucasicum* Küster, 1847b: 98 and *D. sulcipenne* Küster, 1847a: 87. Glabrous form of *D. sulcipenne* was described by Küster as *D. caucasicum* because in the original description of *D. caucasicum* the most typical characters of *D. sulcipenne* were mentioned: well developed lateral thoracic spines and longitudinal elytral furrows - both impossible in *D. cinerarium*. So, *D. caucasicum* Küster, 1847b is a glabrous subspecies of *D. sulcipenne* Küster, 1847a: *D. sulcipenne caucasicum* Küster, 1847b, stat. n. The present situation was supposed by Danilevsky (2007) long ago in his WEB sites, but never published, as he conditionally accepted the name *D. cinerarium caucasicum* Küster, 1847b for a number of Caucasian populations of different species of “*cinerarium*-group”.

Three populations of *D. cinerarium*-group were recently discovered in Armenia by Mark Kalashian and his colleagues (Danilevsky, 2007). They represent three different species and differ from typical European *D. cinerarium cinerarium*, as well as from *D. c. gorodinskii* Danilevsky, 1996 from South Ukraine first of all by the domination of glabrous form of females (which is usually totally absent in *D. c. cinerarium*), and then by relatively smooth elytral and pronotal surface with very fine and sparse punctation, as well as by endophallus structures.

All three forms were not known to Plavilstshikov, none is represented in his collection, neither in the collection of Zoological Museum of Sankt-Petersburg. One of these three species can be identified as *D. kasikoporanum* Pic, 1902 described from Turkey. Two others must be described as new. Breuning (1962) did not mention both in his complete revision of Dorcadionini.

The nomenclature of *D. cinerarium*-group is rather complicated, so it is necessary for the beginning to propose the description of *D. cinerarium* (F.).

Several abbreviations were used in the text:

- AN collection of A. Napolov, Riga (Latvia);
AS collection of A. Shapovalov, Orenburg (Russia);
CH collection of C. Holzschuh, Villach (Austria);
MD collection of M. Danilevsky, Moscow (Russia);
MK collection of M. Kalashian, Erevan (Armenia);
ML collection of M. Lazarev, Moscow (Russia);
MS collection of M. Smirnov, Ivanovo (Russia);
MNHN Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris (France);
MPSU Moscow Pedagogical State University, Moscow (Russia);
ZIN Zoological Institute of Russian Academy of Sciences, Sankt-Petersburg (Russia);
ZMM Zoological Museum of Moscow State University, Moscow (Russia).

RESULTS

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium (Fabricius, 1787)

(Figs 5-15)

Lamia cineraria Fabricius, 1787: 140 („Pallas Icon. tab. F. fi g 11. Habitat in Russia meridionali“).

Lamia tricolor Fischer-Waldheim, 1805: 15 („les environ de Moscou, et du Volga“).

Dorcadion sericatum, Krynicki, 1832: 160, part.; Sturm, 1843: 260 ; Ganglbauer, 1884: 443 („Krim, Caucasus, Kleinasien“), part.

Dorcadion sericatum var. *perroudi* Pic, 1942: 2 (“de Crimée”).

Dorcadion caucasicum, Sturm, 1843: 260; Plavilstshikov, 1927: 5; Zahaikevitch, 1991: 148; Prisyj, 2005: 40.

Dorcadion (s.str.) *caucasicum*, Aurivillius, 1922: 41, part.; Winkler, 1929: 1192; Plavilstshikov, 1931: 74 („Kishinev“); Ogloblin, 1948: 466 (south of European Russia eastwards Dnepr river).

Dorcadion (s.str.) *caucasicum* var. *macropoides* Plavilstshikov, 1932a: 183 („Rossia europ., Ukraina, Izjum prov. Charkov.”)

Dorcadion (Compsodorcadion) caucasicum, Plavilstshikov, 1932b: 193, part.

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium, Breuning, 1946: 117, part.; 1958: 22 (“Crimée, Anatolie sept.”), part.; 1962: 361, part.; Althoff, Danilevsky, 1997: 32; Bartenev, 2004: 37.

Dorcadion (Autodorcadion) caucasicum, Plavilstshikov, 1958: 118, part.; 1965: 412; Lobanov et al., 1982: 263, part.

Dorcadion (Autodorcadion) cinerarium, Danilevsky et Miroshnikov., 1985, 329.

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium gorodinskii, Danilevsky, 1996: 65 (“S Ukraine, Kherson env., Rybalche; Kherson env., Turetsky Val...”), part.

Type locality. Ukraine and South part of European Russia. As it was mentioned above, the picture (Fig. 2) of the lectotype (present designation) was not accompanied by any geographical note, as corresponding part of the manuscript was not published. Until study of the manuscript, preserved in the library of Berlin Zoological Museum, I accept as type locality the European part of South Russia of 18th century (now it is Ukraine and south of European Russia), according to the title of the publication by Pallas (1781): “Icones insectorum praesertim Rossiae Sibiriae peculiarium”.

Diagnosis. The taxon is characterized by moderately big size (to about 15.6 mm), obliterated lateral thoracic tubercles, elytral longitudinal furrows distinct only anteriorly, female elytra usually totally pubescent.

Males (Fig. 5); body moderately narrow; frons with light central stripe; with distinct punctation; vertex glabrous, with moderately dense small punctation; fine white pubescence presents on genae and around eyes; antennae thin, reaching apical elytral third; 1st joint red, dark-red or nearly black, with dense pale recumbent pubescence; prothorax transverse with rough lateral punctation, lateral tubercles wide and obtuse; pronotum densely punctated along middle, with distinct central white line; scutellum triangular, sometimes more elongated, with white pubescence; elytra black, often with reddish apical margin, oval, widened near middle, regularly exposed, with slightly pronounced longitudinal furrows anteriorly; most of elytral surface is usually glabrous; white sutural stripe accompanied by velvety black subsutural stripes; marginal white stripe very narrow; sometimes the traces of reduced humeral and dorsal white stripes can be seen anteriorly; several populations from European coast of Black Sea are characterized by males with totally pubescent elytra (Danilevsky, 1996); a group of such populations from near Kherson (South Ukraine) was described as *D. cinerarium gorodinskii* Danilevsky, 1996; very rare more or less pubescent males can be observed among glabrous specimens in South Crimea; humeral carinae obliterated, dorsal carinae can be slightly exposed only anteriorly; legs usually red, but sometimes nearly black, densely covered with pale pubescence; last abdominal sternite with shallow apical emargination; pygidium and postpygidium widely rounded; aedeagus distinctly sharpened; endophallus (Fig. 6) relatively long and narrow, but shorter than body. Basal tube (bt) much longer its width, straight, with numerous transverse wrinkles; ventral plates (vp) small; medial tube (mt) long and narrow with distinct enlargement near middle; central blabber (cb) poorly developed, partly covered with microspiculae; central trunk (ct) without ventral tubercle, hardly delimited from central bladder, densely covered with very short microspiculae; preapical bulb small, about as long, as wide; apical bulb (ab) narrow, cylindrical.

Females (Figs 7-15); usually autochromal and so normally differ from males by totally pubescent elytra; elytral pubescence usually pale-brown with dorsal and humeral white stripes (Figs 8-11), sometimes dark-brown (Figs 7, 12-13), very rare black without humeral and dorsal stripes (Fig. 14); body wider, antennae reaching elytral middle; head, pronotum and elytra always pubescent in pubescent forms; elytral carinae slightly visible; sutural white stripe usually wider than humeral stripe, humeral stripe usually wider than dorsal; last abdominal sternite widely rounded with small apical emargination, last tergite narrowly rounded; glabrous, androchromal forms of females (Fig. 15) with male type of elytral pubescence are definitely known from Crimea (Belogorsk environs) and Moldova (Rezeny env.).

Body length in males: 9.0-14.0 mm, width: 3.3-5.0 mm; length in females: 9.7-15.6 mm, width: 4.1-6.4 mm.

Distribution. *D. cinerarium* is distributed from Voronezh region of Russia in the north-east to Moldova in south-west and to Ciscaucasia southwards; the east border of the area must be

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Figs5-6; 5- *D. c. cinerarium*, male, Voronezh reg., 20 km N Rossosh. 6 - Endophallus of *D. c. cinerarium*, Krasnyj Sulin distr.; ab- apical bulb; ae- aedeagus; af- apical furrow; ap- apical phallomer; bb- apical bubble; bp- basal phallomer; bt- basal tube; cb- central bladder; ct- central trunk; mt- medial tube; pb- preapical bulb; vp- ventral plate.

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the Volga, no specimens of the species are known eastwards the Volga. Dense populations of *D. cinerarium* are known from many regions of South Russia and Ukraine; the species is very numerous in Crimea.

Known localities are - Russia: Kursk reg. (ZMM); Belgorod reg. (Prisnyj, 2005): south Belgorod env. (private message by A.V. Prisnyj); Novyj Oskol distr., 1 km northwards Belyj Kolodez (private message by A. V. Prisnyj); Veydelevka distr., 2,5 km eastwards Viktoropol (private message by A. V. Prisnyj); Rostov reg.: Taganrog env. (Kasatkin & Arzanov, 1997); Efremovka (Kasatkin & Arzanov, 1997); Fominskij (Kasatkin & Arzanov, 1997); Avilovo-

Uspenskoe (Kasatkin & Arzanov, 1997); Kazachji Lagerja (Kasatkin & Arzanov, 1997); Margaritovka (ZIN); Sinegorskiy (MD); Rostov-na-Donu (Kasatkin & Arzanov, 1997; ZMM); Novocherkassk (ZMM); Krasnyj Sulin distr. (ML); Nedvigovka env. (Kasatkin & Arzanov, 1997; AN); Kamensk-Shakhtinskiy (MPSU); Volgograd reg.: Olkhovka (MD); Kalach na Donu (Kaliuzhnaja et al., 2000), Trekhostrovskaja (Kaliuzhnaja et al., 2000), Golubinskaja (Kaliuzhnaja et al., 2000); Sarepta (ZIN); Kumylga River (MS); Voronezh reg.: Voronezh (private message by S. Negrobov); 30 km southwards Ostorogozhsk (MD), Rossosh (private message by S. Negrobov); 20 km northwards Rossosh (MD); 4 km westwards Marki (private message by S. Negrobov); Varvarino (private message by S. Negrobov); Liski distr., Divnogore (private message by S. Negrobov; MD); Petropavlovka distr., (Negrobov et al., 2005); Nikolo-Varvarinka (private message by S. Negrobov); Belaja Gorka (private message by S. Negrobov); Novovoronezh (private message by S. Negrobov); Burljaevka (private message by S. Negrobov); Medovo (private message by S. Negrobov); Korotojak (private message by S. Negrobov); 2 km S. Gniloe (private message by M. Tzurikov); Drozdovo (private message by M. Tzurikov); Krasnodar reg.: Taman (MD); Anapa (MD); Shkurinsk (Kasatkin & Arzanov, 1997); Novorossiysk env., Markotkh ridge (ZIN, MD); Gelendzhik, Markotkh ridge (ZIN, MPSU); Mingrelskaja (ZMM); Pashkovskaja (ZIN); Adygeya Republic: Maykop (ZMM); Ukraine: Kiev reg.: Kiev env. (ZIN); Lugansk reg.: between Kupiansk and Svatovo (ZMM); Derkul (ZMM); Yunitza (ZMM); Sverdlovsk distr., Provale (Medvedev, 1950); Donetsk reg.: Donetsk (Martynov, Pisarenko, 2004); Shirokino (MPSU); Artemovsk (ZIN, ZMM); Jasinovataja env., Verkhnetoretskoe (Martynov & Pisarenko, 2004); Konstantinovka distr., Stepanovka (Martynov & Pisarenko, 2004); Konstantinovka distr., Kurdjumovka (Martynov & Pisarenko, 2004); Starobeshevo env. (Martynov & Pisarenko, 2004); Dobropole distr., Nikanorovka (Martynov & Pisarenko, 2004); Novoazovsk distr. Khomutovo (Martynov & Pisarenko, 2004); Pershotravnevoe distr., Jalta (Martynov & Pisarenko, 2004); Gorlovka (Martynov & Pisarenko, 2004); Krasnyj Liman distr., Jatzkovka (Martynov & Pisarenko, 2004); Slovjansk (ZMM, ZIN); Tatjanovka (ZIN); Dnepropetrovsk reg.: Tokovskoye (MPSU, ML); Pavlograd (MD, AN); Nikopol env. (AN); Kirovograd reg.: Kirovograd (ZMM, ZIN); Odessa reg.: Odessa (ZIN, ZMM); Ananjevo dist., Dolinskoe (MD); Poltava reg.: Poltava (ZMM), Mirgorod distr., Jareski (ZMM); Kharkov reg.: Kharkov (ZMM); Volchansk (MD, MPSU); Krasnograd (ZMM); Zhitomir reg.: Zhitomir (MD); Zaporozhje reg.: Berdjansk (MD); Melitopol env., Molochny Liman (MPSU); Kherson reg.: Chongar (MD); Turetzky Val (MD); Nikolaev reg.: Nikolaev env. (MD); Nikolaev distr., Parutino (MD); Crimea Republic: Feodosija (ZIN); Luchistoye (MD); Alma river (ZIN); Krasnopeschernaja (ZIN); Miskhor (ZIN); Babugan-Jayla (ZIN); Jalta (ZIN, ZMM, MD); Koreiz (ZMM); Jaltinskaja-jayla (MPSU); Laspi (ZIN); Belokamensk (ZIN); Orlinoye (ZIN); Balaklava (ZIN); Alupka (ZMM); Sevastopol (ZIN, ZMM, MPSU); Mekenzievy Mt. (ZIN), Simeiz (ZMM); Otuzskaja valley (ZMM); Nataschino (ZMM); Foros (ZMM); Simferopol (ZIN, ZMM, MD, ML); Salgirka (MD, ML); Dubki (ZIN); Marino (ML); Lozovoe (ML); Belogorsk, Sary-Kaja (MD, ML); Gaspra (ZIN); Belbek (ZIN); Zaprudnoe (ZIN); Beketovo (ZMM); Alushta (ZIN); Stary Krym (ZIN); Agarmysh (ZIN); Kurskoe (ZMM); Gurzuf (MD); Shebetovka (MPSU); Karadag Mt., 44°54'N, 35°12'E (ZMM); Tarkhankut (MD); Verhnjaja Kutuzovka (MD, ML); Sudak (MD, ML); Argamysh Mt. (MPSU); Vladislavovka (MD); Moldova: Kishinev (Plavilstshikov, 1931); Orkhej (before Orgeev) dist., Korneshty

Figs 7-15. *D. c. cinerarium*: 7- female, 75 km S Voronezh, Divnogorie; 8- female, Rostov reg., Sinegorskiy; 9- female, Simferopol, Salgirka; 10- female, Simferopol, Salgirka; 11- female, Krym, Simferopol; 12- female, Kharkov reg., Volochansk distr.; 13- female, Krym, Simferopol; 14- female, Krym, Sudak; 15- female, Krym, Belogorsk, Sary-Kaja.

(ZIN); between Purkary and Belgorod Dnestrovsky (ZIN), Rezeny (AS,MD, ML).

Material examined. Russia: Kursk region, 1 ♀, (ZMM); Volgograd reg., Sarepta, Khristoforov, 1 ♀, (ZIN); Rostov reg., Margaritovka, 1 ♂, (ZIN); Novorossiysk, 22.iv.1906, 1 ♂, ZIN; Novorossiysk, 1909, N. N. Bogdanov-Katkov, 1 ♂, (ZIN); Don, Novotcherkassk, iv.1917, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀, (ZMM); Anapa, 20.iv.1918, D.Zavileisky, 1 ♂, (MD); Anapa, iv.1919, Arnoldi, 1 ♀, (MD); Rostov-na-Donu, 08.v.1922, 1 ♂, (ZMM); Choper river, Urjupino, 30.iii.1929, A. Menstschikov, 2 ♂♂, (ZMM); Russia, Krasnodar reg., Mingreleskaja, 5-11.vi.1930, Galkin, 9 ♂♂, 1 ♀, (ZMM); Adygeja, Maykop, 20.v.1932, 1 ♂, (ZMM); Rostov reg., Kamensk [now Kamensk-Shakhtinskiy], 23.iv.1950, K. Arnoldi, 3 ♂♂, (MPSU); Rostov reg., Sinegorskiy, 7.v.1972, Lunina, 1 ♀, (MD); Don, Novotcherkassk ot Aksay, 22.iv.1975, 1 ♀, (ZMM); Voronezh reg., 20 km N. Rossosh, 13.v.1980, Anosov, 1 ♂, (MD); 75 km. S. Voronezh, Divnogorie, 6.v.1984, 1 ♀, (MD); Krasnodar reg., Pashkovskaja [now Pashkovskiy], 9.v.1988, E. Stepanov, 1 ♀, (ZIN); 30 km W. Rostov-na-Donu, Nedvigovka, 24.v.1989, A. Napolov, 1 ♀, (AN); Gelendzhik, Markotkh ridge, 21.v.1990, P. Rybnov, 1 ♂, (MPSU); Krasnodar reg., Taman, 24.iv.1992, A. Abramov, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, (MD); Gelendzhik, Markotkh ridge, 11.v.1995, V. Gnezdilov, 1 ♂, (ZIN); Voronezh reg., 30 km S. Ostrogzhsk, 24.iv.1997, Tzurikov, 1 ♂, (MD); Volgograd reg., Olkhovka, 17.v.1997, V. Sychev, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, (MD); Rostov reg., Krasnyj Sulin distr., v.2001, D. Kasatkin, 5 ♂♂, 1 ♀, (ML); Novorossiysk env., Markotkh ridge 600 m, 23-27.v.2007, A. Abramov, 2 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, (MD); Volgograd reg., Novoanennskiy distr., 27 km SSE Novoaninskiy, Kumylga River, 27.iv.2008, M. Smirnov, 4 ♂, (MS); Ukraine: Kiev, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, (ZIN); Crimea, Feodosija, 1 ♂, (ZIN); Crimea, Alma river, Rybakov, 54 ♂♂, 41 ♀♀, (ZIN); - Simferopol, Dubki, 17.iv.1901, Kuznetsov, 1 ♂, (ZIN); Voroshilovgrad [now Lugansk] reg., Kupjansk, Ivanov, 3 ♀♀, (ZIN); Crimea, Jalta, 1.iv.1903 and 22.vii.1973, 1 ♀, (MD); Crimea, Jalta, 12.iv.1904, Suvorov, 1 ♀, (ZMM); Crimea, Agarmysh, 29.iii.1906, Kirechenko, 4 ♂♂, 9 ♀♀, (ZIN); Crimea, Agarmysh, 23-24.iv.1906, 4 ♀♀, (ZIN); Crimea, Laspi, 19-25.iv-v.1907, K. Jatzentkovskiy, 2 ♂♂, (ZIN); Crimea, Belbek, 12-24.v.1907, Kuznetsov, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀, (ZIN); Crimea, Belbek, 14.v.1907, Kirechenko, 6 ♀♀, (ZIN); Crimea, Degermenkoy [now Zaprudnoe], 20.v.1907, Kirechenko, 1 ♂, (ZIN); Cimea, Babugan-Jayla, 18.vi.1911, W. Pliginski, 1 ♂, (ZIN); Crimea, Babugan-Jayla, 19.vi.1911, A. M. Djakonov, 1 ♀, (ZIN); Sevastopol, Mekenziev Mt., 7.iv.1912, W. Pliginski, 1 ♀, (ZIN); Crimea, Koreiz, 16.vii.1912, 1 ♀, (ZMM); Crimea, Sevastopol, 15.iv.1904 and 5.iii.1913, W. Pliginski, 4 ♂♂, 1 ♀, (ZMM); Crimea peninsula, Otuzskaja valley, 12.iii.1916, V. Vuchetich, 1 ♂, (ZMM); Bahmut [now Artemovsk], 6.iv.1892, 1 ♀, (ZIN); Donetsk reg., Slovjansk, 26.iv.1896, Sokolov, 4 ♂♂, 1 ♀, (ZMM); Crimea, Jalta, 12-13.iv.1903, G. Suvorov 8 ♂♂, 6 ♀♀, (ZIN); Crimea, Inkerman [now Belokamensk], 5.v.1903, Kuznetsov, 1 ♂, (ZIN); Odessa, 20.iv.1908, 2 ♂♂, (ZIN); Crimea, Balaklava, Solomko, 1908, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀, (ZIN); Bahmut [now Artemovsk], 30.iv.1908, Walch, 1 ♂, (ZMM); Crimea, Baydary [now Orlinoe], Jacentkovskiy, 25.iii.1907 and 6.v.1907, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, (ZIN); Poltava, 12.iv.1912, Ogloblin, 1 ♂, (ZMM); Crimea, Alupka, 12.v.1912, 1 ♀, (ZMM); Crimea, Kizil-Koba [now Krasnopeshchernaja], 27.v.1912, W. Pliginski, 1 ♂, (ZIN); Crimea, Simeiz, 14-16.iv.1913, D. Romashov, 5 ♂♂, (ZMM); 1 ♂, holotype (monotypy) of *D. caucasicum* var. *macropoides* Plavilstshikov, 1932 with 3 labels: (1), „Cotype“ [red], (2) [„Russia, Chark. d., 24.iii.1916“][in Russia], (3) Holotype, *D. caucasicum* var. *macropoides* Plavilstshikov, 1932 [red], (ZMM); Poltava reg., Mirgorod

distr., Jareski 27.v.1919, 1 ♂, (ZMM); Odessa, 15.iv.1921, D. Znoyko, 2 ♀♀, (ZIN); Kharkov reg., Krasnograd, 1926, F. Lukjanovich, 1 ♀, (ZMM); Crimea, Gaspra, v.1926, V. A. Mindgolm, 5 ♂♂, (ZIN); Crimea, Nataschino, 18.iv.1927, 1 ♂, (ZMM); Crimea, Foros, vi.1930, 1 ♂, (ZMM); Berdjansk, 6.iv.1932, 1 ♂, (MD); Crimea, Simferopol, 9.iv.1932, 10 ♂♂, 20 ♀♀, (ZMM); Crimea, Miskhor, 25.iv.1932, Reykhardt, 3 ♂♂, (ZIN); Voroshilovgrad [now Lugansk] reg., Derkul, 22.iv.1934, A. Alekseev, 1 ♂, (ZMM); Crimea, Kuchuk-Koy [now Beketovo], 11.v.1934, 1 ♀, (ZMM); Crimea, Alushta, 22.iv.1935, Kryzhanovskiy, 1 ♀, (ZIN); Kharkov, 2.v.1936, 3 ♂♂, (ZMM); Odessa, 9.v.1937, 10 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀, (ZMM); Svjatogorsk, Tatjanovka, 17.v.1937, Arnoldi, 1 ♂, (ZIN); Kirovograd, 5.v.1946, 3 ♂♂, 8 ♀♀, (ZMM, ZIN); Crimea, Staryj Krym, 1.vi.1946, 2 ♀♀, (ZIN); Crimea, Gurzuf, 13.iv.1948, K. Arnoldi, 1 ♀, (MD); Zhitomir, vi.1949, S. Nikireev, 4 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, (MD); Voroshilovgrad [now Lugansk] reg., between Kupiansk and Svatovo, 23.iv.1954, G. Mazokhin, 4 ♂♂, 1 ♀, (ZMM); Voroshilovgrad [now Lugansk] reg., Derkul, Yunitza, 27.iv.1954, G. Mazokhin, 17 ♂♂, 6 ♀♀, (ZMM); Crimea, Alushta, 12.v.1955, 1 ♂, (ZIN); Crimea, Karadag Mt., 44°54'N, 35°12'E, 23.04.55 and 22.iv.1956, 9 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀, (ZMM); Crimea, Staryj Krym, Kurskoe, 20.iv.1956, 4 ♂♂, 1 ♀, (ZMM); Crimea, Jaltinskaja-jayla, 3.vi.1976, B. S. Pavlov - Verevkin, 1 ♂, (MPSU); Nikolaev env., v.1977, 1 ♀, (MD); Kherson env., Turetzky Val, iv.1982, 1 ♂, (MD); Kharkov reg., Volchansk, 24.iv.1985, I. Pliushch, 11 ♂♂, 1 ♀, (MD); Kharkov reg., Volchansk, 24.iv.1985, Efremov, 2 ♂♂, (MPSU); Crimea, Tarkhankut, 2.vi.1985, I. Pliushch, 1 ♂, (MD); Crimea, Shebetovka, 26.iv.1986, Bogolilova, 1 ♀, (MPSU); Crimea, Argamysh Mt., 26.iv.1986, I. Korshunova, 1 ♂, (MPSU); Crimea, Simferopol, Salgirka, 5-8.v.1987, K. Efetov, 21 ♂♂, 18 ♀♀, (MD, ML); Dnepropetrovsk reg., Nikopol env., 10.v.-20.vi.1987, J. Tretjakov, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, (AN); Crimea, Alushta, Verhnjaja Kutuzovka, 7.vi.1987, 10.vi.1988 and 8.iv.1989, K. Efetov, 5 ♂♂, (MD, ML); Crimea, Lozovoe, 9.iv.1988, K. Efetov, 2 ♂♂, (ML); Simferopol, 24-29.iv.1988 and 1.v.1991, K. Efetov, 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, (ML); Crimea, Simferopol, Marino, 30.iv.1988, K. Efetov, 1 ♂, (ML); Crimea, Sudak, 3.v.1988, 9.iv.1989 and 14.iv.1991, K. Efetov, 5 ♂♂, (MD, ML); Crimea, Demerdzhi [now Luchistoye], 15.iv.1989, K. Efetov, 1 ♂, (MD); Crimea, Belogorsk, Sary-Kaja, 14.iv.1990, K. Efetov, 2 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀, (MD, ML); Donetsk reg., 12 km E. Mariupol, Shirokino, 29.iv.1990, I. Blonskiy, 1 ♂, (MPSU); Crimea, Vladislavovka, 19.iv.1992, M. Danilevsky, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀, (MD); Dnepropetrovsk reg., Pavlograd, 1-15.v.1993, V. Brigaderenko 7 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, (MD, AN); Holotype: (♂), with 2 labels: (1) "Kherson reg., Rybalche, 28.iv-10.v.95, S. Vaschenko"; (2) "Holotypus, *Dorcadion cinerarium gorodinskii* ssp. n., det. M. Danilevsky, 1996" [red], (MD); Paratypes (2 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀), of *Dorcadion cinerarium gorodinskii* with same geographical label, (MD); Chongar, 25.iv-1.v.1996, R. Mishustin, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, (MD); Nikolaev distr., Parutino, 26.iv.1997, S. Vaschenko, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, (MD); Dnepropetrovsk reg., Tokovskoye, 19.iv.1998, 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, (MPSU); Apostolovo distr., Tokovskoye, 30.iv.1998, 19.v.1998 and 26.iv.2000, 8 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, (MPSU, ML); Odessa reg., Ananjevo dist., Dolinskoe, 2-3.iv.2002, S. Vaschenko, 4 ♂♂, (MD); Melitopol env., Molochny Liman, 25.iv.2004, A. Perevozov, 1 ♂, (MPSU); Moldova: Orgeev dist., Korneshty, 1902, Zubov, 1 ♂, (ZIN); Purkary, Akkerman [now Belgorod Dnestrovskiy], 14.iv.1911, Chernavin, 7 ♂♂, 1 ♀, (ZIN); Rezeny env., 26.iv and 9.v.2006, 14.v.2008, A. Zubov, 55 ♂♂, 16 ♀♀, (AS, MD, ML).

Remarks. *D. cinerarium* differs from Transcaucasian representatives of "*cinerarium*-group" (*D. kasikoporanum* Pic, *D. sisanense* sp. n. and *D. megriense* sp. n.) first of all by very

distinct pronotal punctation, then by wider prothorax, more distinctly developed elytral longitudinal furrows; endophallus with enlargement of medial tube without ventral tubercle of central trunk, with narrow preapical bulb; autochromal pubescent females dominate in all populations.

Males of *D. c. gorodinskii*, described from near Kherson (South Ukraine) are always with densely pubescent elytra. According to Danilevsky (2007): “the area of the subspecies can be enlarged far northwards to about Zaporozhje (1 ♂, Zaporozhjie, Khortitza, 2.v.1968, A. Koval; 1 ♂, Kamenka Dneprovskaja, 5.iv.1973, A. Koval; both in A. Koval’s collection)”.

Several males of *D. cinerarium* with totally pubescent elytra are also known from many localities of the area along European coast of Black Sea (Danilevsky, 1996): Anapa, Taman, Berdiansk, Chongar, Tarkhankut, Nikolaev, Odessa). The taxonomic status of corresponding populations is not clear. Danilevsky (1996) supposed, they can represent several subspecies of independent origin. I also know such pubescent males from south Moldova (Purkary env.) from near Black Sea coast. But in about 40 km from the coast (Rezeny) the populations of *D. cinerarium* are quite typical with glabrous males.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) kasikoporanum* Pic, 1902**

(Figs 16-21)

Dorcadion kasikoporanum Pic, 1902: 10 (“Armenie: Kasikoporan”); Danilevsky, 1992: 110 (Mt. Arailer, Armenia near Egvard)

Dorcadion (s.str.) *kasikoporanum* Winkler, 1929: 1192.

Dorcadion (Autodorcadion) kasikoporanum, Plavilstshikov, 1948: 127 (Iran, NE Turkey), part.; 1958: 123 (Iran, NE Turkey), part.

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) kasikoporanum, Breuning, 1962: 377 (“Kasikoporan beschrieben”).

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) kasikoporanum, Danilevsky et al., 2005: 137; Danilevsky, 2007.

Type locality (Map 3). Turkey, Igdır prov., Kasikoporan, 40°01'N, 43°26'E, 20km W Tuzluca (according to the original description and original label of the holotype).

Type material. Holotype (♂): “Russ Armenia, Kasikoporan, 1901, Korb.”, (MNHN).

Other material studied. “TR. bor. or., GÖLE env., 24.v.1992, J. Macek ”, 2 ♂♂, (CH); Armenia, Mt. Arailer, 1900-2000 m, 19.v.1985, M. Kalashian, 2 ♂♂, (MD); same locality, 25.v.1986, M. Kalashian, 1 ♀, (MD); same locality, 18.v.1994, M. Kalashian, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, (MD); same locality, 29.v.1993, M. Kalashian, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, (MD); same locality, 18.v.1996, M. Kalashian, 1 ♂, (MD); same locality, 2000-2500 m, 18-21.vi.2003, M. Danilevsky, 27 ♂♂, 15 ♀♀, (MD).

Diagnosis. The species is characterized by very smooth pronotum and elytra. Antennae black with red 1st joint, sometimes 3 or 4 basal joints reddish; pronotum and elytra very smooth, strongly shining; pronotum in certain specimens (especially in males) totally without punctures, or punctation very fine and sparse, hardly visible; pronotum always glabrous, without central stripe, often fine central furrow also indistinct; elytral furrows usually also totally indistinct; female elytra sometimes slightly rugose; marginal white stripe very narrow,

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vc

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Figs 16-21. *D. kasikoporanum*: 16- male, holotype; 17- labels of the holotype of *D. kasikoporanum*; 18- male, Armenia, Mt. Arailer, 2000 m; 19- male, same locality; 20- Central trunk of endophallus, same locality, (vc - ventral tubercle); 21- female, same locality.

but sometimes wider (specially in females), extending beyond epipleurae; humeral stripes usually totally absent, but sometimes short strokes can present anteriorly and posteriorly in males and in females; pubescent form of females unknown; legs totally red; central trunk of endophallus with ventral tubercle.

Body length in males: 11.0-14.5 mm, width: 4.0-5.2 mm; length in females: 11.8-15.0 mm; width: 4.7-6.0 mm.

Remarks. The species differs from all other members of “*cinerarium*-group” in Armenia by very smooth, shining pronotum, which is often totally without punctures.

D. kasikoporanum was described from “Kazikoporan” or Kazkoporan - a small village situated in north-west Igdır about 20 km westwards Tuzluca and about 10 km southwards the river Arax at the river Tandurek. The locality is named “Kazykolaran” in Russian topographical military map; same name is used in Russian “Atlas of Car Roads from Atlantic to Pacific Ocean”, 1999, Minsk, “Trivium”: 382 pp.

D. kasikoporanum was wrongly recorded for Talysh Mountains in Azerbaijan (Lobanov et al., 1981, 1982) on the base of specimens described later as *Dorcadion kalashiani* Danilevsky, 1992. *D. kasikoporanum* was also wrongly reported for Iran by Plavilstshikov (1948, 1958) on the base of taxa close to *D. kalashiani*.

Distribution. (Map 3). North-East Turkey, two localities known: Igdır prov., Kasikoporan, 40°01'N, 43°26'E - type locality and Ardahan prov., Göle; Armenia: Arailer Mt., about 20 km north-westwards Erevan, 1900-2500 m, 40°24'N, 44°26'E.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) sisianense sp. n.

(Figs 22-25)

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) cinerarium caucasicum, Danilevsky et al., 2005: 137.

Type locality. Armenia, Sisian Pass, 2 km W Gorajk, 2000 m, 39 40'N, 45°45'E.

Type material. Holotype (♂): Armenia, Sisian Pass, 2 km W Gorajk, 2000 m, 39 40'N, 45°45'E, 25.vi.2003, M. Danilevsky, MD. Paratypes: (8 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀): with same label, MD, ML; (13 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀): same locality, 2000-2200 m, 3.vi.1993, 12.v.1996, 11.v.2001, 10-14.vi.2003, M. Kalashian, MD; (28 ♂♂): same locality, 3.vi.1993, 12.v.1996, 11.v.2001, 26.vi.2003, 6.vi.2006, 7.vi.2007, M. Kalashian, MK.

Description. The taxon is characterized by relatively smooth head, pronotum and elytra.

Males (Fig. 22); body narrow; frons without pale central stripe; with distinct punctation; vertex glabrous, with sparse small punctation; white pubescence absent on genae and around eyes; antennae thick, reaching apical elytral third, black with red 1st joint; prothorax elongated, about as long as basal width, with rough lateral punctation, lateral tubercles very short and wide, obtuse; pronotum smooth, shining, with fine sparse, but distinct punctation; fine central furrow present; central white stripe absent, only small white spot can be visible at base; scutellum glabrous, triangular; elytra black with reddish apical margin, oval, widened near

Figs 22-25. *D. sisianense* sp. n.: 22- male, holotype, Armenia, Sisian Pass, 2 km W Gorajk, 2000 m; 23- endophallus, same locality, (vc- ventral tubercle); 24-25 females, paratypes, same locality.

middle, regularly exposed, with slightly pronounced dorsal longitudinal furrows anteriorly; dorsal furrow with a row of distinct punctures to about middle, but sometimes quite smooth; humeri with distinct punctation disappearing far before middle; most of elytral surface totally glabrous, white sutural stripe accompanied by velvety black subsutural stripes; marginal white stripe very narrow, never extending beyond epipleura; legs red, but tarsi often dark to nearly black; last abdominal sternite with shallow apical emargination; pygidium and postpygidium widely rounded; central trunk of endophallus with ventral tubercle; central trunk of endophallus with ventral tubercle; central trunk of endophallus with ventral tubercle.

Females (Figs 24-25); nearly always androchromal, very similar to males; body wider,

antennae reaching elytral middle; elytral furrows deep; last abdominal sternite widely rounded with small apical emargination, last tergite narrowly rounded; only one autochromal female known with totally pubescent elytra (Fig. 25), head with grey-brown pubescence, vertex with two brown spots, pronotum also with brown pubescence with pale lateral areas; elytra with dark-brown pubescence and pale sutural, dorsal, humeral and lateral stripes.

Body length in males: 10.3-13.5 mm, width: 3.7-4.8 mm; length in females: 14.0-16.5 mm, width: 5.3-6.0 mm.

Remarks. New taxon is very close and similar to *D. kasikoporanum* Pic because of smooth elytra and pronotum, but in *D. kasikoporanum*, the pronotal punctation is usually indistinct, often totally absent, elytral furrows totally obliterated.

D. sisianense sp. n. can be easily distinguished from *D. cinerarium* by relatively smooth pronotum and elytra; central pronotal furrow in *D. sisianense* very fine, sometimes nearly indistinct; white pronotal setae stripe in males absent. Besides, male elytra in *D. c. cinerarium* nearly always have small areas of black pubescence, specially near apices and also white strokes anteriorly; while in *D. sisianense* sp. n., elytra are totally glabrous between marginal and sutural (including subsutural) stripes. Prothorax in *D. sisianense* sp. n. distinctly more elongated than in *D. cinerarium*.

D. megriense sp. n. described below also has glabrous elytra; prothorax also relatively long. *D. sisianense*, sp. n. differs from very big *D. megriense* sp. n. first of all by small body size, and also by much finer pronotal punctation and small thoracic tubercles.

Endophallus of *D. sisianense* sp. n. (personal message by Danilevsky) was described (Danilevsky et al., 2005) under wrong name: "*D. cinerarium caucasicum*".

Distribution. Armenia: Sisian pass, 39°30'N 46°00'E, about 2 km westwards Gorajk; only one population known; the beetles are most numerous around the point of the pass and southwards higher along watershed for about 2 km, as well as for about 1 km downward along east slope to Gorajk.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) megriense* sp. n.**

(Figs 26-28)

Type locality. Armenia, Megri ridge, 5-6 km N Shvanidzor, 38°59'N, 46°23'E.

Type material. Holotype (♂): Armenia, Megri ridge, 5-6 km N Shvanidzor, 38°59'N, 46°23'E, 1500 m, v.2003, Malkhasanian, (MD). Paratypes: (1 ♀): same locality, 24.iv.1998, K. Aghababian, (MD); (1 ♂): same locality, 25.iv.2001, K. Agababian, (MD).

Description. The taxon is characterized by very big size and glabrous elytra in males and in females.

Males (Fig. 26); body wide; frons glabrous, with distinct punctation; vertex glabrous, with moderately dense small punctation; antennae thick, reaching apical elytral third, black with red 1st joint; prothorax elongated, about as long as basal width, with rough lateral

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Figs 26-28. *D. megriense* sp. n.: 26- male, holotype; Armenia, Megri ridge, 5-6 km N Shvanidzor, 1500 m; 27- endophallus, paratype, same locality, (vc- ventral tubercle); 28- female, paratype, same locality.

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punctuation, lateral tubercles well developed, relatively long, but wide and obtuse; pronotum with numerous deep scattered punctures, shining; fine central furrow present; central white stripe absent; scutellum glabrous, with fine white setae; elytra black with reddish apical margin, oval, widened near middle, regularly exposed, with slightly pronounced dorsal longitudinal furrows anteriorly; humeri with distinct punctuation disappearing before middle; most of elytral surface totally glabrous, white sutural stripe accompanied by velvety black subsutural stripes; marginal white stripe a little wider than sutural stripe; legs red, but tarsi darkened, nearly black; last abdominal sternite with shallow apical emargination; pygidium and postpygidium widely rounded; central trunk of endophallus with ventral tubercle.

Female (Fig. 28); unique known female androchromal, very similar to males; body wider,

antennae reaching elytral middle; elytral furrows deeper; last abdominal sternite widely rounded with small apical emargination, last tergite narrowly rounded.

Body length in males: 15.0-15.7mm, width: 5.0-5.5mm; length in female: 16.5mm, width: 6.5mm.

Remarks. *D. megriense* sp. n. differs from close *D. sisianense* sp. n. first of all by big size and then by more distinct pronotal punctation and well developed prothorax lateral tubercles.

Distribution. South Armenia, south slope of Megri pass, 5-6 km northwards Shvanidzor, 38°59'N, 46°23'E.

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Map 1. Localities of *D. cinerarium*. *D. cinerarium cinerarium* (red circles): 1-67; *D. c. gorodinskii* (yellow circles): 78-81, (81 - type locality); *D. cinerarium* ssp.? (grey circles): 68-77. Moldova: 1-3, 77; Ukraine: 4-15, 36-46, 54-56, 70-76, 78-81; (Kirovograd reg.: 4; Zhitomir reg.: 5; Kiev reg.: 6; Poltava reg.: 7, 8; Dnepropetrovsk reg.: 9-11; Kharkov reg.: 12-15; Voroshilovgrad [now Lugansk] reg.: 36, 46; Donetsk reg.: 37-45, 54-56; Zaporozhje reg.: 70-71, 78-79; Kherson reg.: 72, 80-81; Crimea: 73; Nikolaev reg.: 74-75; Odessa reg.: 76) Russia: 16-35, 47-53, 57-69; (Kursk reg.: 16; Belgorod reg.: 17-19; Voronezh reg.: 20-35; Rostov reg.: 47-53, 57; Volgograd reg.: 58-62; Adygea Republic: 63; Krasnodar reg.: 64-69). 1- Orgevskiy distr., Korneshty; 2- Kishinev; 3- Rezeny; 4- Kirovograd; 5- Zhitomir; 6- Kiev env.; 7- Mirgorod distr., Jareski; 8- Poltava; 9- Tokovskoye; 10- Nikopol env.; 11- Pavlograd; 12- Krasnograd; 13- Kharkov; 14 - Krasnyj Liman distr., Jatzkovka; 15- Volchansk; 16- Kursk env.; 17- S. Belgorod env.; 18- Novy Oskol distr., 1km N. Bely Kolodez; 19- Veydelevka distr., 2.5 km E. Viktorpol; 20- Voronezh; 21- Novovoronezh; 22- Bobrov distr., Nikolo-Varvarinka; 23- Kamenka distr., 4 km W. Marki; 24- Ostrogozhsk distr., Korotojak; 25- Ostrogozhsk distr., 2 km S. Gnileo; 26- Liski distr., Divnogore; 27- Liski distr.; 28- Novokhopersk distr., Varvarino; 29- Burljaevka; 30- 30 km S. Ostorogozhsk; 31- Drozdovo; 32- Rossosh distr. NE Rossosh; 33- 20 km N. Rossosh; 34- Boguchar distr. Medovo; 35- Boguchar distr. Belaja Gorka; 36- between Kupiansk and Svatovo; 37- Tatjanovka; 38- Slovjansk; 39- Konstantinovka distr., Stepanovka; 40- Bahmut [now Artemovsk]; 41- Konstantinovka distr., Kurdjumovka; 42- Gorlovka; 43- Jasinovataja env., Skotovatataja [now Verkhnetoretskoe]; 44- Donetsk; 45- Starobeshevo env.; 46- Sverdlovsk distr., Provale; 47- Kamensk [now Kamensk-Shakhtinskiy]; 48- Sinegorskiy; 49- Krasnyj Sulin distr.; 50- Novocherkassk; 51- Rostov-na-Donu; 52- Nedvigovka; 53- Taganrog env.; 54- Novoazovsk distr., Khomutovo; 55- Shirokino; 56- Pershotravnevoe distr., Jalta; 57- Margaritovka; 58- Olkhovka; 59- Trekhostrovskaja; 60- Golubinskaja; 61- Kalach na Donu; 62- Sarepta; 63- Maykop; 64- Pashkovskaja [now Pashkovskiy]; 65- Mingrelskaja; 66- Gelendzhik, Markotkh ridge; 67- Novorossiysk, Markotkh ridge; 68- Anapa; 69- Taman; 70- Berdjansk; 71- Melitopol env., Molochny Liman; 72- Chongar; 73- Tarkhankut; 74- Nikolaev env.; 75- Nikolaev reg., Parutino; 76- Odessa; 77- between Purkary and Akkerman [now Belgorod Dnestrovskiy]; 78- Khortitza; 79- Kamenka Dneprovskaja; 80- Kherson env.; 81- Rybalche.

Map 2. *D. cinerarium*. 1- Tarkhankut; 2- Natashino; 3- Sevastopol; 4- Inkerman [now Belokamensk]; 5- Balaklava; 6- Laspi; 7- Foros; 8- Baydary [now Orlinoe]; 9- Alupka; 10- Simeiz; 11- Miskhor; 12- Gaspra; 13- Yalta; 14- Gurfuz; 15- Degermenkoy [now Zaprudnoe]; 16- Kuchuk-Koy [now Beketovo]; 17- Alushta; 18- Kutuzovka; 19- Demerdzhi [now Luchistoye]; 20- Kizil-Koba [now Krasnopeshchernaja]; 21- Lozovoe; 22- Marino; 23- Dubki; 24- Simferopol; 25- Sudak; 26- Kurskoe; 27- Stary Krym; 28- Karadag Mt., 44°54'N, 35°12'E; 29- Feodosija; 30- Vladislavovka.

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Map 3. Transcaucasia; *D. megriense* sp. n. (1), *D. sisianense* sp. n. (2), *D. kasikoporanum* (3-5).
 1- Armenia, Megri ridge, 5-6 km N Shvanidzor, 38°59' N, 46°23' E; 2- Armenia, Sisian Pass, 2 km W Gorajk, 39°40' N, 45°45' E; 3- Armenia, Arailer Mt., 40°24' N, 44°26' E; 4- Turkey, Igdır prov., Kasikoporan, 40°01', 43°26' E (type locality); 5- Turkey, Ardahan prov., Göle.

Photo 1-3. 1- Armenia, Arailer Mt., area of *D. kasikoporanum* (photo by M. Yu. Kalashjan). 2- Armenia, the top of Arailer Mt., 2200 m, locality of *D. kasikoporanum* (photo by M. L. Danilevsky). 3- Armenia, Sisian Pass, 2000 m, type locality of *D. sisianense* (photo by M. L. Danilevsky).

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